

Unique Approaches in Educating the Youth in The Spirit of Perfection and in identifying their talents

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Abstract:

This article deals with the reforms in youth policy in our country, the implementation of targeted programs among young people, the development of education, culture, science, literature, art and sports, the improvement of state youth policy.

Keywords: sports, football, psychological training, process, children,

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Introduction

The Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 18, 1993 "On measures to further develop football in the Republic of Uzbekistan" is of great importance in the development of football in our country. Sports games as a means of physical and psycho-functional improvement of the body are very popular among various categories of the population, especially among schoolchildren, so their main ones - volleyball, basketball, football, handball, etc. included in the study plans.

The needs of every individual for performing in a particular sport are different from those of another. If we take the example of the sprint event, even a small difference in time and speed or distance decides the performance record, victory or defeat. The difference depends on individual-specific capabilities. It is, therefore, necessary to identify the individual potential during the training. By identifying their needs, training may be focused at improving the identified gaps in the abilities of that sports person.

The issues of proper use of all conditions created for young people, which can be the basis of the development of Uzbekistan, the proper organization of their development in the spirit of patriotism were discussed. Timely implementation of measures to prevent the problems of young people in science, the implementation of targeted programs, education, culture, science, literature, identified in five priority areas of the Action Strategy for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, developed by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, development of arts and sports, improvement of state youth policy are important issues. [1]

Necessary conditions have been created for the population, especially the younger generation, to engage in regular physical culture and mass sports. Modern sports complexes have been built in cities and villages. It would be expedient to select talented children and organize new methods of working with them, based on ideas. Physical education of school-age children constitutes an individual health-improving education system.

Daily classes are held with each child according to the established rules. In children's childhood, their favorite toy was the ball, which they have loved since childhood. It is a purposeful approach to the field of football to maintain this passion and interest, to ensure that they are regularly engaged in the learning process. Sports training is a special process of preparation of sports persons based on scientific principles aimed at improving and maintaining higher performance capacity in different sports activities. It is a particular type of training designed to improve fitness and abilities to perform in a given sport. It includes strength in training, corrective and restorative exercises, conditioning and cardiovascular training. It also includes mental and psychological training and advise on nutritional values. [3]

In recent years, certain work has been done to provide comprehensive support to the youth of our country, to protect their rights and interests. Strengthening the spiritual immunity of young people, meaningful spending of their free time is an urgent issue. The head of our state put forward five important initiatives to organize work in the social and spiritual spheres on the basis of a new system.

Methods

There are various methods of sports training that are mentioned below: continuous training method, circuit training method, interval training method, ply metric training method, repetition training method, weight training method, fatlike training method, cross training method, however in this chapter only two methods are described:

1. Interval Training: It involves maximum intensity work with intervals. This intensity work is alternated with periods of rest or low activity so that the body adjusts to work and rest. This method involves more of cardiovascular activities of individual.

2. Cross Training: refers to training in different ways to improve the overall performance. Cross training uses different methods collectively to improve fitness and increases effectiveness of the training process for every human.

Serves as a means of stopping, receiving and possessing the ball. The purpose of stopping is to slow down the ball as it rolls or flies to make the next move. The term "stop the ball" is sometimes used in the sense of "adjusting the ball" or "receiving the ball." Therefore, when considering ways to stop the ball, we mean that the player does not stop the ball completely, but adapts it for the next move. [2]

Results and discussion

The main goal of the radical changes in the economy is to further improve the living standards of the population, our youth, to improve their well-being. As a vital proof of this, small business and private entrepreneurship, which are an important factor in the sustainable development of our economy today, have become an important area for increasing the social activity of our youth, demonstrating entrepreneurship, entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship. With the personal care of the head of our state, the creation of new jobs for our youth, preferential loans for entrepreneurship and running their own businesses are all creative work to ensure the active participation of our youth in social life.

Confidence in young people, who are the main creative force in the development of our society, means, first of all, confidence in our great future. After all, a great future is created by great people. Today, our young people are stepping towards greatness.

Its foundations are being built on the basis of the courage, noble deeds and confidence of our people in the future.

At the same time, thanks to our independence, all the material and spiritual factors for the development of young people, the upbringing of a harmoniously developed generation are becoming a priority in all areas of our ongoing reforms.

Every young man and woman who feels such attention and care will undoubtedly have a deeper understanding of his duty and responsibility to the motherland and the people. Feelings of inspiration lead to a combination of a sense of pride and arrogance with patriotism, humanity, devotion and creativity. Development of projects "Physiological and pedagogical features of the selection of gifted and talented young players" further development of the future will ensure a worthy assessment of the talents of young people. [4]

The project works with young people who are currently or want to play football. On the basis of the project, planned classes, various trainings based on a unique approach to working with gifted children, mental walks to get acquainted with the thinking and

worldview of children. The project includes the program of a preventive seminar on the process of enriching the perception of talented young people about football and the demonstration of their talents.

Three variants of seminars of different duration on each topic are given. This will shape the worldview and patriotic feelings of the future players of the football team to be formed. [5]

Conclusion

Sports games as a means of physical and psycho-functional development of the body are very popular among various categories of the population, especially among schoolchildren, so its main ones are included in the programs of multi-stage competitions and educational institutions of volleyball, basketball, football, handball.

In times of football formation, team captains monitor compliance with the rules of the game. The referee appeared on the football field in 1880, and a year later the referee began to appear on the field with two assistants. The organization of full trainings on the formation of the game of football in children and the demonstration of their skills will expand the opportunities. Technical skills form the basis for a successful tactical concept of the game. The main goal, which focuses on the principle of teaching and improving technical knowledge, is to correctly solve situations that are relevant to the game situation during the competition.

Adaptation is defined as the adjustment of physical and psychological functional systems to the training load. Adaptation to a load results in the enhancement of performance capacity. Thus, a sports person is able to increase his/her performance as a result of adaptation process. Adaptation process demands that a sports person maintains regularity in training. If a sports person is exposed to new and unfamiliar load in a systematic planned way, the adaptation process will be faster. [6]

REFERENCES

- Mirziyoyev Sh. We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people. – Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2017.
- Karimov I.A. Let the ideology of our society serve to make the people - the people, the nation - the nation // "Tafakkur". –1998, – №2.
- Shodmonqulov A. Individual and society. – Tashkent: Sharq, 2010. – 240 p.
- Collection of normative documents of higher education. – Tashkent: Sharq, 2001.
- Pavlov Sh.K., Abdurakhmanov F.A. Preparation of hand-lists. – Tashkent: UzGIFK, 2006.
- Ignateva V.Ya., Petracheva I.V. Many years of preparation of handball players in DYuSSh. – Moscow: Soviet sport, 2003.

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